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Title

Capitalizing on the Learning Potential of Intentional Networks to Advance Leadership for Equity

Div A Section 3 - District Improvement

Abstract

This study examines how intentional networks—collaborative partnerships designed to address complex challenges—expand school districts’ capacity to promote equity-centered leadership. Guided by social network theory and extant literature on relational structures, we thematically analyzed 25 semi-structured interviews with central network actors. Findings identified conditions that facilitated and constrained the network’s potential to promote district learning and change. A shared equity vision, trusting relationships, and structured opportunities for collaboration supported systems-level change, while limited partner engagement, deliverable-driven priorities, and capacity constraints hindered progress. Central actors played a critical role in fostering trust, aligning efforts, and promoting accountability. The study highlights how network design and relational dynamics shape efforts to advance equity-focused leadership in complex educational systems.